

Pachamama worldview and the decolonial challenge of an emerging legal paradigm
Cosmovisión Pachamama y el desafío decolonial de un paradigma jurídico emergente

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Abstract: This article analyzes the philosophical, legal, and political foundations that support the transition from the anthropocentric paradigm of domination to the institutionalization of the Rights of Nature. Based on the premise that the modern capitalist model has triggered a profound socio-environmental crisis, the study highlights the inadequacy of the concept of sustainable development, whose utilitarian ethics proves to be merely palliative. In contrast, an epistemological rupture emerges in Latin America, grounded in the indigenous worldview of *Pachamama* (Mother Earth), endorsed by the New Constitutionalism. The research is qualitative, with a historical-evolutionary approach, based on bibliographic and documentary analysis. Constitutional texts, critical legal doctrine, decolonial epistemologies, jurisprudence, and official sources were examined, with emphasis on the Constitutions of Ecuador (2008) and Bolivia (2009). The findings indicate that recognizing Nature as a subject of rights is not a mere extension of Environmental Law, but a paradigmatic shift that challenges the colonial foundations of legal dogmatics. The constitutionalization of the principles of *Pachamama* and *Sumak Kawsay* and *Suma Qamaña* in Latin American constitutions inaugurates a new pluralistic, ecocentric, and intercultural legal model, proposing the restoration of the relationship between humanity and Nature, with political, epistemic, and civilizational implications.

Keywords: Rights of Nature; Nature as a subject of rights; *Pachamama*; *Sumak Kawsay*; Decoloniality; New Latin American Constitutionalism.

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1. Introduction

This article analyzes the inadequacy of the current concept of sustainable development, which, anchored in the modern rationality of the commodification of Nature, heir to Cartesian enlightenment and mechanistic science, has consolidated an ontological split between humans and Nature. This has legitimized the unrestricted exploitation of ecosystems, causing an unprecedented socio-environmental crisis on planet Earth.

The research will be conducted using a historical-evolutionary approach, aiming to analyze the new scientific model emerging in Latin America and the foundations of the worldviews of the Andean-Amazonian native peoples that support the institutionalization of the Rights of Nature in the Constitutions of Ecuador and Bolivia.

The research technique employed is qualitative, examining constitutional texts, critical legal doctrine, and decolonial epistemologies through the consultation of books, websites, newspaper articles, academic papers, official journals, scientific periodicals, laws, and jurisprudence.

The objective of this article is to analyze, through bibliographic and documentary research, the philosophical, legal, and political foundations that support the transition from the anthropocentric paradigm to the institutionalization of the Rights of Nature, based on the concepts of *Pachamama* (Mother Earth) and *Sumak Kawsay* (*Buen Vivir*).

Initially, it will analyze how the anthropocentric paradigm, consolidated in modernity, transformed Nature into a mere object of exploitation, prioritizing human progress at the expense of ecological balance, which has deepened the current environmental crisis.

Next, this article will present principles such as *Pachamama* and *Sumak Kawsay*, derived from the worldview of the Andean-Amazonian native peoples, which recognize Nature as a subject of right.

Finally, it will analyze the New Latin American Constitutionalism, based on the Constitutions of Ecuador (2008) and Bolivia (2009), which incorporate a new pluralistic and decolonial model of sustainable development, aiming for ecological balance and the valorization of interculturality among their nationals.

2. Nature as object and the anthropocentric paradigm

Since the beginning of modernity, and especially after the industrial revolution, developmentalist logic has adopted the theory of domination, which entails the appropriation of Nature with a market-oriented bias, aiming to provide goods and services through industrialized processes of production and consumption.

The theory of domination places the human being in a privileged position, as the only entity endowed with intrinsic value and capable of granting value to others, while all other entities are mere objects endowed with instrumental value; that is, they have value only to the extent of human needs, desires, and utility (Gudynas, 2015).

This theory, of Judeo-Christian origin, was taken to the extreme during the Renaissance by Francis Bacon, who proclaimed that science should torture Nature, just as the inquisitors of the Holy Office did with their defendants, to force it to reveal its last secrets (Acosta, 2012, p. 55).

With the advent of modernity and the consolidation of scientific thought, Nature, once conceived as a sacred, nurturing, and nourishing entity with which humans maintained a relationship of respect and reverence, began to be treated as a wild entity that had to be dominated and converted into an inexhaustible source of resources for human consumption.

René Descartes (1999, p. 62), with his maxim "I think, therefore I am" affirmed that the human being, having the exclusive attribute of the "rational soul" was superior

to any other corporeal matter in the world, and was therefore legitimized to exclude Nature from his sphere of morality. Nature came to be understood not as a living organism, but as an inert substance devoid of soul, that is, a *res extensa* (extended thing) that could be dismantled and manipulated, as it was destitute of any intrinsic purpose (Boff, 2009).

This paradigm provided the epistemic basis for the domination and subjugation of natural entities, reducing them to mere objects of exploitation, available for appropriation and use by human beings in the name of material progress and social well-being. The value of things began to be measured by a purely economic aspect, such that Nature was cataloged and broken down into components, which came to be called resources – that is, legal goods, because they are useful and have economic value (Gudynas, 2015).

The anthropocentric paradigm promotes a profound ontological rupture between the human being and Nature, such that humanity, which once marveled at the diversity of life, now values its uniformity and places itself in a superior central position, alienated from the very Nature of which it is a part (Guerra Filho, 2011).

In the context of emerging capitalism, what Max Weber called the "disenchantment of the world" occurred, where Nature came to be considered exclusively from an instrumental perspective – that is, as a mere source of raw materials, devoid of any symbolic, aesthetic, or spiritual value, and stripped entirely of its cultural and existential meanings (Unger, 1991, p. 45).

The enlightenment reason, Cartesian determinism, and Baconian physics, by basing themselves on the total separation between humans and Nature, sought to unravel its mysteries, subjugating and dominating it. This ultimately influenced all legal science, which came to be conceived as a system of laws legitimizing the exclusion of Nature from our sphere of moral consideration (Fernandez; Lima, 2020).

This model of scientific development is embedded in the modern paradigm and is characterized by specialization, objectivity, linearity, and a dualistic separation between the subject and object of knowledge (Santos, 1988).

Thus, the principle of sustainable development is linked to a market-based order that aims for economic growth capable of satisfying the needs of the present generation without compromising the capacity and rights of future generations. The value of the environment is intimately linked to the economic benefits resulting from the use of natural resources and, principally, the perception of this use as an essential condition for economic growth.

This principle does not question the logic of capital accumulation or the commodification of Nature; on the contrary, it sophisticates it, creating new concepts like "environmental services", "carbon credits" and "green economy", which ultimately deepen the subordination of ecosystems to market logic (Gudynas, 2015).

Sustainable development, therefore, seeks the sustainability of development, not the sustainability of life in its entirety, making it just a palliative that aims to mitigate the "collateral damage" of the system, without questioning the legitimacy of the system itself (Latouche, 2009).

By ambiguously reconciling the classic notion of development – historically associated with continuous economic growth and often accompanied by negative environmental impacts – with the notion of environmental sustainability, which presupposes containing ecological degradation and limiting polluting emissions, this principle creates an intrinsic tension and duality that highlights a fundamental paradox at its very conceptual core (Vilela et. al., 2002).

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3. Nature as a subject of rights and the emergence of a new decolonial environmental paradigm

The current environmental and civilizational crisis stems not from a mere natural event, but from a crisis of perception, as the current global society interacts with the world from a fragmented, mechanistic, and reductionist perspective, ignoring other life systems, which cannot be understood in isolation as they are interconnected and interdependent (Capra; Luisi, 2014).

The current climate and environmental crisis has a spiritual dimension, as the degradation of ecosystems is a consequence of a flawed perspective that demands a paradigmatic shift and a new way of thinking about and valuing the interconnection and interrelationship between humans and Nature (Unger, 1991).

This new paradigm emerges not from economic structures, but from a profound experience of reverence and sacredness before the mystery of the universe and life, and from a spirituality that recognizes the Sacred in the totality of existence.

The opportunity for rethinking and hoping that the current crisis provides is the positive outcome that must result from elevating our state of consciousness, not from technoscience; that is, it must result from a feeling of belonging to spiritual values that help humanity seek innovative solutions (Boff, 2009).

The recognition of Nature as a subject of right does not constitute a mere expansion of Environmental Law, but a radical challenge to Western legal dogmatics based on a new relational and ecocentric ontology.

This epistemological shift incorporates the concepts of *Pachamama* (Mother Earth) and *Sumak Kawsay* (*Buen Vivir*), where Nature is seen as a sacred spiritual entity endowed with intrinsic value and recognized as a subject of right that participates in the ecological community in a reciprocal relationship with human beings.

Such an approach does not represent a mere extension of classic Environmental Law, but a fundamental questioning of the colonial foundations of modern legal dogmatics, aiming to overcome the palliative model of sustainable development and embrace the pluriversality expressed by the New Latin American Constitutionalism.

For the Amerindian peoples, Nature is Mother Earth (*Pachamama*), a Divine entity that protects agriculture and ensures nourishment, fertility, and abundance, but also the generating and sustaining force responsible for maintaining life on the planet (Paredes, 1920).

Pachamama is the existence of two fundamental forces: a cosmic force from the sky and a telluric force from the earth, which are considered the two energies responsible for the process of life, and are interrelated through the principle of AYNI, symbolizing complementarity and reciprocity among all beings (Aymara Huanacuni Mamani, 2010).

In this worldview, humans and Nature mutually interrelate through a life in harmony, as Nature depends on a "human non-doing" – materialized in respecting its cycles of regeneration – and on acting conservatively to maintain ecological balance (Ávila Santamira, 2011).

The cosmology of Brazilian indigenous peoples, such as the Krenak, for example, believes that we are inserted into a larger organism, the Earth, of which we are all children. Here, *Pacha* is the womb of consciousness, where life is not instrumental or utilitarian, but the fruit of an intrinsic relationship with the origin, with the memory of the world's creation, and with the welcoming symbolic narratives that each culture has produced over time (Krenak, 2022).

Pachamama, by aiming to restore the harmony and balance of life, is strictly linked to the paradigm of *Sumak Kawsay*, in the Quechua language, or *Suma Qamaña*, in the Aymara language.

Sumak Kawsay (*Buen Vivir*) is an ancestral communitarian philosophy of life that holds specific meanings for various native peoples, representing a common horizon and a new relationship between humans and Nature (Huanacuni Mamani, 2015).

This is not the literal, traditional "common good" limited to humans, but the well-being of all living beings, where reverence for *Pachamama* must be accompanied by the fundamental rule of *Sumak Kawsay*. In essence, this represents not an individual morality, but an ethic that guides the actions of the State and the interactions among individuals in their relationship with Nature (Zaffaroni, 2011).

This diversity of terms and meanings allows us to find equivalences and similarities in the search for unity. In the Quechua language, *Sumak* means ideal, realization, good; while *Kawsay* means dignified life – that is, a life that must be lived in harmony and balance between all and the Universe (Kowii, 2011).

In its etymology, *Qamaña* holds the meaning of "to live," "to dwell," "to care for others," and "to coexist with Mother Earth," while *Suma* means "good," "perfect," "lovely," "precious." Thus, *Suma Qamaña* takes on the meaning of "knowing how to live together" and "mutually supporting one another" (Albó, 2009).

Created by Aymara intellectuals, these expressions are not part of the daily language of native peoples and serve only as a vindicatory ideal for some leaders, activists, and intellectuals in the process of enshrining their rights in the Bolivian Constitution (Uzeda, Vasquez, 2009).

For native peoples, the quality of life should not be measured by the economy, but by a deeper essence of life, where *Buen Vivir* does not mean having a better life than others, but overcoming competition and comparison in favor of communion with others – a perspective that can only be realized collectively, not individually (Albó, 2009).

The principle of *Buen Vivir* is a critique of individualism, based on a new paradigm guided by the essential principles of balance, harmony, creativity, and "knowing how to be", opening paths in the search for *Sumak Kawsay* (Dantas, 2012).

It is a profound relationship with *Pachamama* – that is, with the cosmic forces of the Universe and with Divinity – aiming to promote a life in constant harmony with the whole, through sacred rites that constantly renew our connection with the Divine (Boff, 2009).

The adoption of the *Sumak Kawsay* principle requires a profound shift in consciousness toward the meaning of life and the destruction of old anthropocentric structures, to build in their place a new civilizational paradigm based on the central value of life, where no one wins if their neighbor does not also win (Santos, 2007).

By breaking with the classic visions of development associated with economic growth and linear progress, *Sumak Kawsay* aims to become an "alternative to development", a radically distinct option from current ideas of sustainable development (Acosta; Gudynas, 2011, p. 81).

In this view, environmental sustainability cannot be reconciled with the logic of economic expansion above all else, which challenges the principle of "sustainable development" and the notion that a full life is conditioned on the progressive accumulation of material goods (Rocha; Lessa, 2021).

The native peoples of Latin America propose an authentic paradigmatic revolution, a true ecocentric turn capable of making a culture of life prevail, in its indissociable vision of interdependence, correlation and complementarity with all beings (Moraes, 2013).

A deep knowledge of Nature and the ability to interpret the signs it manifests can only be achieved through intercultural dialogues between different peoples and communities in their ancestral relationships with the natural environment.

Pluralistic collectivities, bearers of diverse knowledge, philosophies, and technologies, whose worldviews offer complementary perspectives, are indispensable for a broader and more integrated understanding of environmental dynamics (Martinez, 2011).

The consistency and consciousness of the knowledge of these populations are salutary, as they have resisted legal anthropocentrism and its colonizing vision in favor

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of an ecocentric view that salvages the culture and cosmology of native peoples (Fernandes; Lima, 2020).

4. Pachamama, Sumak Kawsay, Suma Qamaña and the New Latin American Constitutionalism

The territories occupied by Latin American native peoples conserve about 80% of the planet's biodiversity, demonstrating that environmental protection is intrinsically linked to the preservation of ancestral cultures and the recognition of *Pachamama* as a subject of right (Gordilho; Muñoz Caron, 2023).

From this worldview of the Andean-Amazonian native peoples emerges a new type of constitutionalism in Latin America, radically distinct from the dominant colonial paradigm.

This is not mere folklore or cultural curiosity, but a complex and sophisticated philosophical system that proposes a relational ontology based on interdependence, reciprocity, and harmony among all beings that make up the cosmic community.

The legal pluralism enshrined by this New Constitutionalism is the legal-normative formation of a new civilizational paradigm in which the State does not create a new subject of rights *ex nihilo* (out of nothing) but rather recognizes the pre-existence and legitimacy of ancestral ontologies and normative orders, historically suppressed and subalternized by the colonial project.

It is a movement aimed at overcoming social and economic inequalities and expanding forms of popular participation to achieve citizen well-being through self-knowledge and the recognition of the ethnic diversity and plurality of Latin American countries (Mercado, 2013).

The legal and political process of promulgating the new constitutions of Bolivia and Ecuador entailed the abandonment of the classic liberal model and, consequently, of their condition of subalternity in relation to foreign legal doctrines.

Although still anchored in a positivist perspective, these new constitutions are revolutionary to the extent that they seek to autonomously build legal solutions adequate to local realities (Lessa; Rocha, 2018).

The Constituent Assemblies of these countries created original and plural texts, attending to local peculiarities, where native peoples with different socio-cultural characteristics, previously excluded from the national founding process, had their rights recognized as fundamental rights (Tarrega; Freitas, 2017).

This decolonial perspective gave rise to a new constitutional political conception, based on interculturality, legal pluralism, and plurinationality, grounded in respect for differences and the deconstruction of historical inequalities. Marginalized and segregated sectors were included in the political-legal sphere, based on a "constitutionalism from below" (*constitucionalismo desde abajo*) (Wolkmer; Fagundes, 2013, p. 339).

By moving away from the liberal anthropocentric paradigm, the New Latin American Constitutionalism has made an important contribution to universal constitutional law. By incorporating the Andean-Amazonian worldview, it directs the production of knowledge toward pluricentrism (Câmara; Fernandes, 2018).

In Ecuador, the Constitution was ratified by a significant majority in a referendum on September 28, 2008, and became, through Articles 10, 71 and following (inserted in Chapter VII), the first in the world to recognize the Rights of Nature.

From its preamble, it recognizes *Pachamama* and various other forms of religiosity and spirituality, breaking with the traditional view of the natural sciences that define the environment only as the sum of biotic and abiotic elements within an ecosystem. In addition to biodiversity, human beings, and their relations with the territory and communities, it includes the spiritual beings of the native peoples (Acosta; Martínez, 2011).

Article 10 of the Constitution of Ecuador expressly recognizes the plurality of subjects and cultural expressions of existence, in addition to Nature's status as a holder of the rights recognized by the Constitution.

In Article 71, it reaffirms the right of Nature, determining full respect for its existence, as well as its maintenance and regeneration – not only of endangered species and natural reserves, but of the ecological rights founded on the Andean worldview of *Pachamama* and its idea of unity and interconnection among all beings (Solon, 2019).

The right to the integral conservation of Nature, however, is not to be confused with integral preservation and the "untouched Nature" concept, which only aims to ensure the use of natural resources for human purposes. It intends to safeguard the integrity of the ecosystems themselves, not isolated individuals (Acosta, 2011).

The Rights of Nature do not aim to end productive processes necessary for a nation's progress, but to replace them with a development model that adapts to the fruitful conservation of their ecological contexts (Gudynas, 2010).

To achieve its rights, Nature must be represented by persons, communities, peoples, or nationalities, and must have the incentive of the State in promoting popular awareness and protection mechanisms.

By granting Nature the right to restoration, without linking it to compensation owed to individuals or collectivities for environmental damages that affected them, Ecuadorian law makes its break from the anthropocentric perspective clear. In this conception, Nature has value in itself and, in case of damage, must be duly restored to its original state (Article 72).

By providing for the right of all persons, peoples, communities, and nationalities to enjoy the environment and the natural wealth that allows them Good Living, Article 74 reinforces the right to conservationism.

The non-appropriability of environmental goods inaugurates a fundamental constitutional mandate for the "statization" of Nature, prohibiting the adoption of market criteria for environmental services. Even if this does not mean disregarding their economic value, their production, benefit, use, and exploitation must be regulated by the State (Acosta, 2012).

Buen Vivir is also present in the preamble of the Constitution of Ecuador, a concept forged in the heat of popular struggles, especially by native peoples, who in their search for alternative ways of life developed an ethic based on the actions of the State and of people among themselves, especially in their relationship with Nature (Zaffaroni, 2011).

The philosophy of *Buen Vivir*, expressed in the practices of the Andean-Amazonian native peoples, not only promotes a harmonious relationship with Nature but also reveals a model of effective sustainability.

The rights to *Buen Vivir* and to a healthy and ecologically balanced environment were provided for in Article 14 of the Constitution of Ecuador. They cover a wide range of rights, among which the right to water stands out as a fundamental and inalienable human right, in addition to the rights to food, communication, education, housing, health, and energy.

Article 11 of this Constitution declares that the Rights of Nature and the rights of *Buen Vivir* are inalienable, indefeasible, indivisible, and interdependent, and possess equal value and priority, breaking with the classic conception of a hierarchy of rights.

Article 275 reinforces the value of interculturality, respect for diversity, and harmonious coexistence with Nature, guaranteeing people, peoples, and communities the effective enjoyment of their rights.

From a political standpoint, for the fruitful implementation of *Buen Vivir* as an alternative to development in the mold of a market society, there is a long way to go, given that the word *desarrollo* (development) appears in the constitutional text 121 (one hundred twenty-one) times, while the terms *Sumak Kawsay* only 5 (five) and *Buen Vivir* 23 (twenty-three) times (Rocha; Lessa, 2021).

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Another model constitution of the New Latin American Constitutionalism is the new Political Constitution of the State of Bolivia. It did not expressly enshrine the Rights of Nature, but it provided for the objectives and functions that guide its public policies toward *Buen Vivir*. Its preamble, along with its principles, provides for harmony and equity in the search for *Buen Vivir*.

After various social struggles led mainly by native peoples, a popular consultation on the new Constitution obtained 61.43% of the votes, and it was promulgated on February 7, 2009, becoming the first Bolivian constitution legitimized directly by popular vote.

Suma Qamaña (*Buen Vivir* in Aymara) appears in the section on the fundamental bases of the State and in Chapter II, which addresses the principles, values, and ends of the State. In Article 8, *Suma Qamaña* is presented as one of the ethical-moral principles of the plural society, along with other similar principles, available in the Quechua and Guaraní languages: *ñandereko* (harmonious life), *tekokavi* (good life), and *qhapajñan* (noble life).

These principles are placed at the same hierarchical level as other classic principles, such as unity, equality, inclusion, dignity, freedom, solidarity, reciprocity, respect, social and gender equity in participation, common well-being, responsibility, social justice, among others.

All of them are directly related to the economic organization of the State. Article 306 points to changes in the path of development, based on a plural economic model oriented toward improving the quality of life and the ~~Good Living~~*Buen Vivir* of the Bolivian people.

According to Article 313 of said Constitution, to achieve ~~Good Living~~*Buen Vivir* in its multiple dimensions, the economic organization must have, among others, the purpose of generating social products, redistributing wealth, and industrializing natural resources.

Article 80, in turn, places education as a central basis for forming a critical social consciousness of life and for life, with a view to ~~Good Living~~*Buen Vivir* and the conservation and protection of the environment, biodiversity, and the territory.

Suma Qamaña and the other associated concepts seek to delineate the structures of a plurinational society, which recognizes 36 (thirty-six) different languages of the native peoples and the existence of different nations and cultures with their own identity and a common essence for a life in harmony and balance with Nature.

Buen Vivir constitutes a distinct form of ontological presence that profoundly redefines the concepts of development and the State. Its incorporation into these Constitutions represents a political-epistemic milestone of great relevance that destabilizes neocolonial foundations and critically challenges liberal thought and traditional political projects (Escobar, 2010).

For the first time, a Bolivian Constitution includes expressions in the languages of native peoples, establishing ethical-moral principles (Huanacuni Mamani, 2010), making evident the cultural resistance of the Andean peoples, even after more than five hundred years of colonialism, neocolonialism, genocide and domination (Zaffaroni, 2011).

In any case, the Constitution of Ecuador, with the "positivization" (legal enactment) of the Rights of Nature, and the Constitution of Bolivia, with the Plurinationalism expressed through *Suma Qamaña* in its multiple expressions, have promoted a new legal theory from a decolonial perspective.

The jurisprudence of the Inter-American Court of Human Rights (IACHR) itself, influenced by the New Latin American Constitutionalism, has advanced toward the recognition of the Rights of Nature, as occurred with Advisory Opinion OC-23/17, which recognized that the environment has intrinsic value, independent of its utility to human beings, paving the way for the enshrinement of the Rights of Nature in the Inter-American system (Gordilho and Breillat, 2024).

5. Conclusion

The challenge facing contemporary legal dogmatics is to recognize the legitimacy of other forms of knowledge and existence, overcoming the monoculture of modern legal knowledge.

The constitutionalization of the Rights of Nature, inspired by the worldview of *Pachamama* and the principle of *Sumak Kawsay* or *Suma Qamaña*, represents a paradigmatic shift in the legal field.

By recognizing Nature as a subject of rights, the Constitutions of Ecuador and Bolivia not only broaden the scope of environmental protection but also destabilize the colonial, anthropocentric, and monist foundations of modern law.

It is a decolonial strategy that redefines the tools of Western constitutionalism to introduce the ontologies of native peoples into legal language, making way for a normative pluriverse. This transformation is not only normative but also political and epistemic, as it proposes a new rationality based on interdependence, reciprocity, and the sacredness of life.

Nature, as a living and sacred entity, demands not only protection but also respect, listening, and coexistence. Law, in this new horizon, must be an instrument of reconnection and not of domination.

This decolonial perspective challenges the dominant paradigm and forces us to recognize the validity of pre-existing Andean cosmologies as a starting point for including Nature in our sphere of moral consideration.

It is an ingenious decolonial strategy, as it re-appropriates and resignifies the "master's tools" – the Western legal-constitutional framework – with the objective of dismantling the "master's house" itself, which is the monist, anthropocentric, and colonial structure of law.

This hybrid nature, which articulates a Western legal form with an indigenous ontological content, gives it transformative potential, based on a New Law that translates, into a legal language intelligible and decodable by the global legal system, a set of cosmological conceptions that can inspire and lend legitimacy to socio-environmental development.

The constitutionalization of *Pachamama* and *Sumak Kawsay/Suma Qamaña* transcends the merely normative dimension to become a political-epistemic project that challenges the supposed universality of Western legal thought, opening space for the construction of a legal world in which multiple ontologies, knowledge systems, and ways of life can coexist harmoniously and equitably.

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